

Allelopathic effects of weeds on germination and seedling vigor of hybrid rice

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Parthenium hysterophorus and *Lantana camara* are common weeds in the Chhattisgarh region of India, where the area under high-yielding rice varieties is increasing rapidly. The allelopathic effects of *Parthenium* and *Lantana* have been reported on many crops but not on hybrid rice (Narwal 1994, Oudhia and Tripathi 1999). To discover the allelopathic potential of *Parthenium* and *Lantana* leaves and *Parthenium* flowers on germination and seedling vigor of hybrid rice var. Proagro 6111, a pot experiment was carried out at the IGAU.

To prepare extracts, leaves of *Parthenium* (PL) and *Lantana* (LL) and flowers of *Parthenium* (PF) were collected randomly from fields. The crushed leaves and flowers were allowed to stand for 24 h in distilled water in the ratio of 1:5 (20%), 1:10 (10%), 1:15 (6.7%), and 1:20 (5%) [1:10 (5%) for PF and LL] of weed material and water, respectively. Extracts were decayed at room temperature (28 ± 1 °C). After decaying, extraction was done with a 2-mm mesh sieve. A bioassay was done in earthen pots filled with neutral clay loam soil and uniformly fertilized with 16, 18, and 12 ppm of urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash, respectively. Rice seeds were soaked in the different extracts or distilled water (control) for 24 h. After soaking, 20 rice seeds were sown in each pot. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with two replicates and was repeated twice. Germination was recorded at 5, 7, 9, and 11 d after sowing (DAS) and root and shoot lengths and dry matter accumulation at 11 DAS.

The different aqueous extracts of *Parthenium* and *Lantana* produced negative and positive allelopathic effects on germination and seedling vigor of rice seeds (see table). At 5 DAS, the aqueous extract of PL (5%) produced a significantly higher

germination than the rest of the treatment combinations except PL (10%) and PF (10%). At 11 DAS, the highest germination was noted in the control and PL (5%), and the lowest in PL (6.7%) and PF (10%). PL (5%) had the longest root and LL (10%) the shortest root. PL (20%) and PL (6.7%) resulted in maximum and minimum shoot length, respectively. PL (5%) had a shoot length comparable with that of PL (20%). PL (20%) and PF (10%) produced the highest and lowest dry root weight, respectively, whereas PL (5%) and PF (10%) showed the highest and lowest dry shoot weight, respectively.

The negative (stimulatory) allelopathic effects of different aqueous extracts of PL on field crops have been reported (Oudhia and Tripathi 1999). Many allelochemicals—e.g., parthenin, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid, coronopillin, and sesquiterpene lactones—from the aqueous extracts of *Parthenium* responsible for positive (inhibitory) allelopathic effects have also been reported (Narwal 1994). In this experiment, the effects of these allelochemicals were significant up to 6.7% concentration. At lower concentration (i.e., 5%), the phytotoxic effects of these allelochemicals were not observed.

Some growth-promoting substances such as glucose, galactose, and potassium chloride in the diluted aqueous extracts of PL have also been reported (Rastogi and Mehrotra 1991). This is probably why the aqueous extract of PL (5%) generally produced germination comparable with that of the control, and higher root and shoot elongation and dry matter accumulation.

The study indicated the possibility of using the aqueous extract of PL at lower concentrations (e.g., 5%) to promote early germination and vigor of rice seeds and seedlings in place of water alone through soaking treatments. The effects of this promising extract on ultimate crop production are under study. Repetition of this work using different hybrid rice varieties and different concentrations would provide a better understanding of allelopathy.

References

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Allelopathic effect of weeds on rice seedlings.

Treatment	Germination (%)				Root length (cm plant ⁻¹)	Shoot length (cm plant ⁻¹)	Root weight (mg plant ⁻¹)	Shoot weight (mg plant ⁻¹)
	5 DAS ^a	7 DAS	9 DAS	11 DAS				
T1 = <i>Parthenium</i> leaves (20%)	66.7	83.3	86.7	86.7	5.95	9.40	33.25	9.33
T2 = <i>Parthenium</i> leaves (10%)	73.3	80.0	83.3	86.7	6.58	7.52	25.17	5.89
T3 = <i>Parthenium</i> leaves (6.7%)	63.3	70.0	73.3	76.7	7.06	5.98	20.55	6.33
T4 = <i>Parthenium</i> leaves (5%)	86.7	93.3	93.3	93.3	8.06	8.35	32.61	12.61
T5 = <i>Parthenium</i> flowers (10%)	76.7	83.3	76.7	76.7	5.80	6.85	18.75	4.17
T6 = <i>Lantana</i> leaves (10%)	53.3	73.3	80.0	80.0	5.73	7.00	21.64	6.15
T7 = Control (soaked in water)	50.0	80.0	93.3	96.7	7.84	6.63	24.22	5.40
LSD (0.05)	20.7	ns	ns	8.1	1.62	2.17	7.28	3.65

^aDAS = days after sowing.